

Improving Bounded Model Checking based on the Hierarchy of Temporal Properties

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Abstract. Bounded model checking (BMC) aims at checking whether a model satisfies a property. A closer look to the literature reveals that most of the existing approaches to solve SAT-based BMC rely on generic strategies, that is supposed to work for any SAT problem. The key idea defended in this paper is to tune SAT solvers algorithm by exploiting both static and dynamic information coming either from the model or the property. For the model, we propose a static classification based on the variables used to encode the BMC into a SAT problem. For the property, we propose to exploit deeper the static hierarchy of Manna and Pnueli [29] that classifies any property expressed through Linear-time Temporal Logic (LTL). By combining these two information with the classical Literal Bloc Distance value (LBD) [40], we are able to design new heuristics well suited for solving BMC problems. In particular, our work is based on the identification of relevant learnt clauses. Our experiments over a large database of BMC problems, show promising results and highlight the importance of considering the structure of the underlying problem in SAT procedures.

Keywords: Bounded model checking, Boolean Satisfiability, Structural information, Linear Temporal Logic, Optimization

1 Introduction

Model checking [9] is a verification technique (fully automated procedure) to establish the correctness of hardware and software systems that range from the simple program that runs a microwave to the very complex software driving a nuclear power plant, passing by our smartphones and cars. In contrast to testing, it is a complete and exhaustive method. Nowadays, along with testing and static analysis, model checking is an essential industrial tool for eliminating bugs and increasing confidence in hardware designs and software products.

Usually, the studied program (model) is expressed in a formal language (e.g., SMV [31], Verilog [32], Promela [24], etc.), while the property is expressed as a temporal logic formula (e.g., LTL [36], CTL [10], PSL [16], etc.). A property

is said to be verified if no execution of the model can invalidate it, otherwise it is violated. To achieve this verification, two approaches have been considered: explicit model checking and symbolic model checking. In explicit model checking, the behaviour of the model as well as the property to be check are represented as automata (a Kripke structure for the model [2] and a Büchi automaton for an LTL property [42]). Then, a synchronous product is performed between the Kripke and the automaton of the (negated) property. If the product is empty, the property is verified, otherwise it is violated. On the other hand, symbolic model checking represents states implicitly using Boolean functions (BDD [5], SAT-based Bounded model-checking [3]). Thus, it helps to fight the well known state-space explosion problem since it does not require the storage of all the state-space explicitly during the traversal.

Regardless of the used technique, properties are expressed using temporal logic. In this paper, we focus on the Linear-time Temporal Logic (LTL) since it expresses many properties of interest and has been extensively studied [29, 1, 34]. For instance, Manna and Pnueli [29] established a full hierarchy of the properties that can be expressed using LTL. This hierarchy has already been adopted [35, 15, 17] in order to tune the performance of model-checkers. The goal of this paper is to exploit the structure of the BMC problem given by: (1) the LTL property classified according to the hierarchy of Manna and Pnueli (Section 2), (2) a characterization of the variables in the context of SAT-based Bounded model checking (Section 3). Sections 4 and 5 give a preliminary study that define relevant information. Section 6 explains how the usage of these information can improve the global performance of modern SAT solvers. Experiments and conclusion are presented in Section 7 and Section 9, respectively.

2 Manna & Pnueli Hierarchy

LTL is a temporal logic that specifies (infinite) sequences describing system behaviors. Lamport [27] partitioned the properties expressed by LTL into two classes: safety (*some bad thing never happens*) and liveness (*some good thing eventually happens*). To illustrate these classes, two main temporal operators are used: **F** (*Finally something happens*) and **G** (*Globally something holds*). For example, one can specify some atomic proposition “ $a = 42$ ” (e.g., variable a is equal to 42) must hold at every point in time (i.e., **G** “ $a = 42$ ”) or eventually holds at some future point in time (i.e., **F** “ $a = 42$ ”).

Based on the combination of the two precedent operators, Manna and Pnueli [29] refined the Lamport’s partitioning into six categories:

- *Safety* (**S**): similar to the one described in the Lamport [27] classification.
- *Guarantee* (**G**): some good thing happens at least once in the future.
- *Obligation* (**O**): combines safety and guarantee properties. This enforces more restrictions on the sequences leading to some good thing.
- *Persistence* (**P**): at some point, a good thing will happen and hold forever.
- *Recurrence* (**R**): some good things will appear infinitely often.

Fig. 1. Hierarchy of Manna & Pnueli

- *Reactivity* (**T**): combines recurrence and persistence properties. This enforces more restriction on the sequences between good things.

This classification establishes the hierarchy depicted in Figure 1. Thus, we have: $\mathbf{S} \cup \mathbf{G} \subseteq \mathbf{O} \subseteq \mathbf{R} \cup \mathbf{P} \subseteq \mathbf{T}$, where each partition is defined by a combination of temporal operators. Each one has inherent characteristics that can be exploited to tune the performance of model-checkers. And to the best of our knowledge, this information has never been exploited to improve SAT-based Bounded model checking!

3 SAT-based Bounded model checking

To verify if an LTL property holds on a system, existing model-checking approaches [5, 7] explore all (infinite) sequences resulting from the combination (synchronized product) between a representation of the LTL property (a Büchi automaton) and a representation of the system (a Kripke structure). These approaches suffer from the well known state-space explosion problem [11] but can be tackled using SAT-based Bounded Model Checking (BMC) [4, 8, 44, 20]. It has a low memory footprint thanks to (1) the restrictions of the verification to sequences bounded by some integer k , and (2) the use of Boolean Satisfiability (SAT) techniques to solve the BMC problem.

Given a model M , an LTL property p , and a bound k , SAT-based BMC approach builds a propositional formula representing the combination ($M \otimes p$) of M and p , both unrolled up to k steps. The formula is said to be satisfiable iff there exists a violation of the property (counter-example) of maximum length k . Otherwise, it is unsatisfiable and the property is verified up to length k .

To encode the Boolean formula of the synchronized product, one can use classical algorithms [41, 25]. These algorithms translate a graph $(M \otimes p)$ to a set of constraints (called *clauses* in the SAT context) that are a disjunction of variables. The final Boolean formula is represented in the form of a conjunction of clauses and can be solved using state-of-the-art SAT procedures. Those based on the well known Conflict Driven Clause Learning algorithm [39] are of particular interest in this work.

Conflict Driven Clause Learning (CDCL) [45]. The majority of the complete state-of-the-art sequential SAT solvers are based on the CDCL algorithm [30, 39] that is an enhancement of the DPLL algorithm [12, 13]. CDCL algorithm performs a backtrack search; selecting at each node of the search tree, a decision literal which is set to a Boolean value. At each decision, a Boolean Constraint Propagation procedure (also called **unit propagation**) is applied. It forces (in cascade) the values of the variables in unit clauses, i.e., clauses that are composed of a single literal. In case of conflict, two situations can be observed: the conflict is detected without making any decision, thus the formula is declared UNSAT; otherwise, a new asserting clause is derived by the **conflict analysis** and the algorithm backjumps to the assertion level [30]. If there is no conflict, a new decision literal is chosen (heuristically) and the algorithm continues its progression. When all variables are assigned, the formula is said to be SAT.

The Learning Mechanism. The effectiveness of CDCL algorithm lies on the learning mechanism. Each time a conflict is encountered, it is analyzed (by the conflict analysis procedure) in order to compute its actual reason, called **learnt clause**. While present in the system, this clause will avoid the same mistake to be made another time, and therefore allows faster deductions (during conflicts analysis and unit propagation steps). Since the number of conflicts is very huge (in avg. 5000/s [40]), controlling the size of the database storing learnt clauses is a challenging task. It can dramatically affect the solver’s performances. Many strategies and heuristics have been proposed to manage the cleaning of the stored clauses. One of the state-of-art strategies uses the Literal Block Distance (LBD) measure [40], that shows its effectiveness in numerous practical cases.

4 A peek inside SAT-based BMC problems

The main goal of this paper is to identify relevant information that can be used to enhance CDCL-based SAT solving in the context of BMC problems. We identify two sources of information, *static information* and *dynamic information*:

Static BMC-based information

- **Variable-based classification:** When translating the high-level description of the problem into a Boolean SAT problem, we can partition

Fig. 2. The seven disjunctive classes of clauses according to the combination of variables they handle: model variables (blue), fresh/junction variables (yellow) and property variables (red).

the variables into three disjoint sets: \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{J} and \mathcal{P} where \mathcal{M} (model) is a Boolean representation of the original variables of the Kripke structure, \mathcal{J} (junction variables) is a set of fresh variables used to finalize the conversion into a Boolean formula, and \mathcal{P} (property) the set of variables used to translate the Büchi automaton of the (negated) property. Hence, any clause (we note by \mathcal{C} , a set of clauses) can be classified according to the variables it handles ($\mathbf{Var}(\omega)$, $\omega \in \mathcal{C}$). Let us denote the classes (highlighted in Figure 2) by:

$$C_X = \{\omega \in \mathcal{C} \mid \forall v \in \mathbf{Var}(\omega), v \in X\}$$

where X is either \mathcal{P} (the property), \mathcal{M} (the model), \mathcal{J} (the fresh variables for the model), \mathcal{PJ} (property and fresh variables), \mathcal{PM} (property and model variables), \mathcal{MJ} (model and fresh variables) or \mathcal{PMJ} (property, model and fresh variables).

- **LTL hierarchy:** When solving a BMC problem, the LTL formula is known *a priori*. We can apply the syntactic characterization of Manna and Pnueli (described in Section 2) in order to compute statically its corresponding class in the hierarchy and thus benefit from this information to propose a parametrization specific to each category of the LTL hierarchy.

Dynamic CDCL-based information

- **Literal block distance (LBD) [40]:** is a positive integer, that is used as a learnt clause quality metric (the less the better) in almost all competitive CDCL-like SAT solvers. The LBD of a clause can change overtime and it can be (re)computed each time the clause is fully assigned.
- **Learnt clauses databases:** During CDCL-solving, every time a new clause is generated, its LBD is computed. According to this value, the usefulness of the clause is guessed and a storing strategy is then applied: when considering MapleCOMSPS [28], one of the best solvers in the

world⁴, it will promote the clause at hand into one of its three databases: **core** ($LBD \leq 3$) for the really important clauses (never deleted), **tier-2** ($LBD \leq 6$) for not-yet-decided clauses, and **local** database for the remaining clauses. Clauses in **tier-2** can be promoted to the **core** database or downgraded to **local** database while those of **local** database can either be promoted to **tier-2** or permanently deleted. Recall that learnt clauses are generated in the *conflict-analysis* procedure of the CDCL algorithm while used in both *unit propagation* and *conflict-analysis* steps.

In this paper we propose to exploit and combine the aforementioned (static and dynamic) information in order to build new heuristics dedicated to SAT-based BMC problems.

5 A study of BMC problems

This section aims to analyze the relation between static BMC-based information and Dynamic CDCL-based information. The derived information will be exploited further in Section 6.

Benchmark setup. To study the characteristics of BMC problems, we developed a tool called BMC-tool⁵ that involves NuSMV tool [6] and MapleCOMSPS [28] SAT solver. The tool takes three parameters as input: (1) an SMV program, (2) an LTL property, and (3) a bound k , required for any BMC problem. It then produces a DIMACS [25] file (representing the SAT encoding formula of the BMC problem at hand) that is processed by (our modified version of) MapleCOMSPS solver.

Our benchmark is composed of 1200 problems. All SMV instances come either from the SMV hardware verification problems [6], the BEEM [33] database, or the RERS Challenge⁶. The LTL properties have been generated using Spot [14] such that, each category of the Manna&Pnueli hierarchy is equivalently represented (200 formula per category). Finally, all the experiments of this paper were conducted on an Intel Xeon machine and a time limit of 2 hours⁷.

Measures. To evaluate the importance of the information presented in Section 4, we built a *training benchmark* for each category of LTL property, composed of 30% of the associated benchmark (62 problems per category). For all instances of the *training benchmark*, we logged the information related to each learnt clause when used in the *unit propagation* and *conflict analysis* with its corresponding LBD value. Thus, the usage rate of each of the classes

⁴ Winner of the main track of the SAT competition 2016 and used as core engine for the best solvers in the last 5 years

⁵ <https://gitlab.lrde.epita.fr/akheireddine/bmctool>

⁶ RERS models translated in NuSMV: <https://tinyurl.com/29a4jcme>

⁷ For a description of our setup, detailed results and code, see <https://akheireddine.github.io/>

Fig. 3. Measures on the *training benchmark* showing learnt clauses usage in propagation (left) and conflict analysis (right) phases for guarantee, obligation, recurrence and reactivity problems. Each class of clauses is colored and annotated by its LBD value.

Fig. 4. Selectors as defined in this paper

Fig. 5. Selectors in MapleCOM-SPS (state-of-the-art)

C_X (in propagation and conflict procedures) are computed by accumulating all the clauses of the same class for the same LBD value.

Figure 3 depicts this rate for guarantee, obligation, recurrence and reactivity categories⁸. The x-axis reports the cumulative mean percentage of learnt clauses for the *training benchmark* and the y-axis corresponds to the cumulative mean usage percentage (left-side for *unit propagation* and right-side for *conflict analysis*). Each point represents the used percentage of learnt clauses of a certain LBD (from 1 to 10) for a certain class⁹. For example on the recurrence curves, the purple triangle with left annotation 6 shows 2.5% of learnt clauses of class \mathcal{PM} , have an $LBD \leq 6$ and are used in 12% of the *unit propagation* time (resp. 14.8% of *conflict analysis* time).

From this figure, we can observe that C_P class always stands out. Nonetheless, the importance of the remaining classes seem to vary according to the group of property that is checked: C_{PJ} is poorly used by both guarantee and obligation, while on recurrence, it has an usage similar to C_P .

6 Contribution

From the above study, we can observe that focusing only on the LBD hides some relevant information. For instance, the classical LBD value for the core database ($LBD \leq 3$) on the obligation-propagation curves, represents 8.1% of learnt clauses for 76.4% of usage. A closer look to Figure 3 reveals that half of this usage came from the C_P class and represents only 1.3% of the learnt clauses. Therefore,

⁸ We do not show persistence and safety since they have the same trend than the presented properties.

⁹ For the sake of readability, we only display LBD values up to 10 (we went up to 50 in practice)

filling the core database with $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ with $LBD \leq 4$ could bring up to 19% usage for less than 1% of learnt clauses.

The idea defended in this paper is: even if the generic characterization of learnt clauses ($LBD \leq 3$) works efficiently for most of the SAT problems, it may not be the most suitable for BMC problems.

Our contribution offers an opening toward new ideas on the identification of good **selectors** (a specific LBD value for each class of clauses and the handled LTL property) for the core and tier-2 databases. These selectors will identify and protect from deletion, new sets of clauses that are relevant during the SAT resolution. Typically, a selector would be of the form: protect $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ clauses with $LBD \leq 8$ and $C_{\mathcal{J}}$ clauses with $LBD \leq 2$, etc.

In this section we propose two heuristics for building efficient **selectors** for core and tier-2 databases depending on the information collected during the training phase. Figure 4 details such a pair of selectors while Figure 5 presents the traditional generic selector used by MapleCOMSPS. This latter is extracted from several studies [40, 28] and show the relevance of clauses with $LBD \leq 3$ and $LBD \leq 6$ to prune the learnt clause databases.

The following approaches are built around the resolution of a linear mathematical program that produces optimal solutions w.r.t the objective(s) and the fixed constraints. Through this study, we propose:

- a simplified approach with no specific constraint on the generated solutions.
- and a more sophisticated and constraining approach, that integrates additional information induced by the previous study (see Section 5).

The comparison of these two strategies will measure once again the importance of a prior and thorough study of the original problem.

Important. It is worth mentioning that the proposed approaches do not rely on a specific SAT solver and can be implemented on top of any CDCL-based SAT solvers.

6.1 Size-based heuristic H_{size}

As pointed previously, the strategy simply computes a set of solutions optimizing two measures: maximizes the total usage rate and minimizes the number of involved learnt clauses, with no additional constraints. Thus, we face a bi-objective system that will enumerate all possible cases (all possible value LBD for each class C_X) and returns only interesting (non-dominated) solutions. Each of these solutions represents a selector. The set of solutions defines a Pareto front depicted in Figure 6 (red points) for the obligation class using the training data collected during the propagation procedure. One can observe that all red points dominate the classical selectors. i.e., for a percentage of learnt clauses similar to $LBD \leq 3$, the percentage of usage is improved. In this case, there is a selector that has 1% less clauses for 2% more usage.

Figure 6 depicts the Pareto front for the unit propagation phase only, but we could also build such a front for the conflict analysis phase. This situation leaves us with two Pareto fronts. Each one provides optimal solutions on the propagation step only or on the conflict analysis step only. To overcome the dilemma on which Pareto front to use, we project each solution of one front into the other one by keeping, at the end, only non-dominated solutions on both sides. Thus, we end up with a unique Pareto front that is a trade-off between solutions provided by both propagation and conflict analysis procedures.

Fig. 6. Measures of learnt clauses usage on Obligation properties during propagation phase. Blue dots denote LBD while red points depict the Pareto front of H_{size}

From there, we can determine the corresponding core selector over a panel of solutions. We opted for the one that approximates the number of involved learnt clauses of the traditional selector ($LBD \leq 3$) but with a gain on the usage rate. We proceed similarly for the tier-2 selector by approximating the amount of learnt clauses of $LBD \leq 6$. The method we opted to choose a selector raises an interesting question: for a similar amount of learnt clauses, does the tuned selector (based on classification of clauses) is more pertinent than traditional selector? Experiments on Section 7 answers the question.

Discussion. When picking the tier-2 selector, we may obtain an *incompatible solution*. For instance, the tier-2 selector can choose to *take* $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ clauses with $LBD \leq 4$ while the core selector specifies $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ clauses with $LBD \leq 8$. This situation may occurs since the Pareto front computation is agnostic and does not filter solutions based on the selector found for the core database. To handle this case, we could adjust the problematic classes of the tier-2 selector by a single increment of their values in core selector. In our experiments this situation never occurs.

6.2 Ratio-based heuristic H_{ratio}

The second strategy offers another way of finding interesting selectors for the databases. The goal is to guide the linear program to exploit the specific features of the studied problem and thus, reach a more suitable solutions. The approach is based on the overall usage rate of a clause $\mathbf{R} = \frac{\%usage}{\%learnt}$. Precisely, the new linear program is a mono-objective system that searches for a solution maximizing the ratio \mathbf{R} w.r.t two additional constraints to guide the search-space:

1. Constraint that try to reduce the total number of learnt clauses to be at worst case, similar to the traditional selectors.
2. Constraints that reflect the importance of each class of clauses. Indeed, little attention to Figures 3 show that some classes seem to be more relevant than others (e.g., class $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ for obligation). This importance may have a significant

influence on the resolution of the linear system. Consequently, we associate a probability to each class C_X according to their relevance in the curve. The probability is computed by taking the ratio of all the LBD of a given class and then normalizing on the 7 classes. Thus, for each class with a probability greater than a given threshold, we constraint the linear program to generate selectors with an LBD at least equivalent to the reference selector (LBD \geq 3 for the core and LBD \geq 6 for tier-2).

As a result, the program provides a unique selector for the core database and we proceed the same way to compute the tier-2 selector.

Discussion. Similarly to the previous strategy, the approach provides us with two selectors: the optimal solution for the conflict and the optimal one for the propagation. Naturally, we opt for the solution that has the best ratio on both sides.

6.3 Combining heuristic and Manna & Pnueli hierarchy

The two aforementioned strategies could be applied directly from the training benchmark [26] (without distinction between category of the hierarchy of Manna&Pnueli) or at finer grain regarding the category of the handled LTL property. From this latter, we are able to calculate an adequate selector for each category. This results in six selectors per heuristic depicted in Table 1.

Table 1 recalls the state-of-the-art selectors and the resulting selectors (for the core and tier-2 databases) from the two heuristics H_{size} and H_{ratio} for all LTL categories, i.e., **S**, **G**, **O**, **R**, **P** and **T**. A selector is described as a set of values, each corresponds to a class of a clause C_X . The value 20 of the column \mathcal{J} (first line of the table) means that the core selector will protect all the clauses of type \mathcal{J} ($C_{\mathcal{J}}$) with an LBD \leq 20. Note that some configurations exhibit the ∞ symbol meaning that all clauses of this class are protected on the corresponding database. For a given selector, we displayed 3 data:

- the size (%learnt) of learnt clauses, i.e., the amount of learnt clauses generated by the selector;
- the usage (%usage) of learnt clauses, i.e., the number of time these clauses are used in the conflict (conf.) and in the propagation (prop.);
- the ratio (**R**) is obtained by dividing the two previous information for the conflict (conf.) and in the propagation (prop.).

At first sight, our two strategies produce selectors that highly contrast from state-of-the-art selectors. Indeed, the generated values can go up to ∞ and down to 1 while the state-of-the-art selector is stable. Typically, H_{size} heuristic reveals a big interest for the $C_{\mathcal{J}}$ class.

A comparison between H_{size} heuristic with the reference gives approximately the same number of learnt clauses but for a better usage rate in favor of our heuristic. A comparison of H_{ratio} heuristic with the reference shows a better ratio with a drop of the learnt clauses rate. When comparing the two heuristics of this paper, it appears that, theoretically, H_{ratio} seems more pertinent than H_{size} . With no surprise, Section 7 confirms its efficiency in practice.

		\mathcal{J}	\mathcal{M}	\mathcal{MJ}	\mathcal{P}	\mathcal{PJ}	\mathcal{PMJ}	\mathcal{PM}	%learnt	%usage		R		
										conf.	prop.	conf	prop.	
H_{size}	G	core	20	3	2	3	4	2	4	10.1	72.6	79.5	7.2	7.9
		tier-2	∞	5	5	5	8	6	10	20.9	20.1	17.6	1.0	0.9
	S	core	1	3	2	4	3	2	4	11.1	72.0	79.4	6.5	7.1
		tier-2	∞	∞	∞	6	8	5	7	17.2	17.8	16.1	1.0	0.9
	O	core	9	5	20	6	3	2	3	7.9	73.2	77.6	9.3	9.9
		tier-2	6	∞	14	11	8	4	7	17.3	19.2	17.5	1.1	1.1
	P	core	4	3	3	5	3	2	4	13.6	75.6	81.3	5.5	6.0
		tier-2	∞	4	6	8	8	5	7	20.2	16.9	15.3	0.8	0.8
	R	core	3	9	2	3	3	2	4	9.5	59.5	70.3	6.3	7.4
		tier-2	∞	∞	6	6	7	5	8	18.8	26.6	23.5	1.4	1.2
	T	core	5	4	1	4	3	2	5	7.4	69.5	77.5	9.4	10.5
		tier-2	∞	7	7	7	5	6	7	11.2	16.5	15.4	1.5	1.4
H_{ratio}	G	core	3	2	2	3	4	3	3	10.2	70.6	79.3	6.9	7.8
		tier-2	6	6	4	5	8	5	10	18.7	21.2	17.3	1.1	0.9
	S	core	1	3	1	4	2	2	4	10.1	68.9	73.6	6.8	7.3
		tier-2	2	6	4	6	7	5	7	17.7	20.7	21.7	1.2	1.2
	O	core	1	5	2	4	3	2	3	7.3	72.0	76.5	9.9	10.5
		tier-2	3	19	3	11	7	5	6	16.7	19.9	18.4	1.2	1.1
	P	core	3	2	3	4	4	2	3	13.1	73.6	80.5	5.6	6.1
		tier-2	∞	4	5	9	7	5	7	19.5	18.6	15.8	1.0	0.8
	R	core	4	4	3	3	3	2	4	9.8	59.5	71.1	6.1	7.3
		tier-2	6	9	5	5	7	5	8	17.2	25.6	22.1	1.5	1.3
	T	core	7	3	2	3	3	1	4	5.9	63.5	72.5	10.7	12.7
		tier-2	∞	6	3	6	6	5	7	11.7	21.5	19.8	1.8	1.7
Reference Heuristic	G	core				3			10.2	70.5	79.1	6.9	7.7	
		tier-2				6			20.7	21.3	17.4	1.0	0.8	
	S	core					3			10.3	68.0	78.0	6.6	7.6
		tier-2					6			17.9	21.6	17.4	1.2	1.0
	O	core					3			7.9	71.6	76.5	9.1	9.7
		tier-2					6			17.4	20.4	18.4	1.2	1.1
	P	core					3			13.8	73.1	80.3	5.3	5.8
		tier-2					6			20.1	19.0	16.0	0.9	0.8
	R	core					3			10.3	58.0	70.8	5.6	6.9
		tier-2					6			18.2	27.0	22.3	1.5	1.2
	T	core					3			6.6	62.1	72.5	9.4	10.9
		tier-2					6			12.0	22.9	19.8	1.9	1.7

Table 1. Comparison of selectors presented in this paper with the state-of-the art selectors. Each of these selectors is associated to the information coming from the training benchmark: %learnt corresponds to the number of learnt clause, %usage is the usage rate in conflict and in propagation, ratio corresponds to the overall usage of a clause. Columns 4 to 10 describe precisely the LBD value associated to each class of clauses.

Solver	Manna&Pnueli H.	UNSAT	SAT	TOTAL	PAR-2
MapleCOMSPS	G guarantee	72	89	161	189h07
	S safety	54	24	78	534h51
	O obligation	44	119	163	163h54
	P persistence	80	62	142	264h26
	R recurrence	23	117	140	264h49
	T reactivity	77	80	157	191h19
	total	350	491	841	1608h43
MapleCOMSPS- H_{size}	G guarantee	70	89	159	197h14
	S safety	58	25	83	522h54
	O obligation	42	120	162	166h14
	P persistence	81	65	146	256h05
	R recurrence	23	116	139	266h37
	T reactivity	79	82	161	177h52
	total	353	497	850	1586h55
MapleCOMSPS- H_{ratio}	G guarantee	70	90	160	196h11
	S safety	56	28	84	524h08
	O obligation	42	120	162	168h09
	P persistence	80	63	143	263h26
	R recurrence	23	119	142	257h25
	T reactivity	81	84	165	165h49
	total	352	504	856	1575h07

Table 2. Comparison between state-of-the-art MapleCOMSPS solver and H_{size} and H_{ratio} heuristics

7 Benchmark

This section presents the evaluation of the two heuristics discussed in this paper, H_{size} and H_{ratio} on the full benchmark presented in Section 5.

Table 2 details the results of our experiments on top of MapleCOMSPS solver. For each class of the hierarchy and for each strategy, we display the number of UNSAT and SAT solved instances, the total number of solved instances and the PAR-2 metric used in SAT competitions¹⁰.

The two proposed heuristics outperform the classical MapleCOMSPS strategy on both SAT and UNSAT problems. Indeed, H_{size} -based strategy solves 3 UNSAT and 6 SAT instances more with a PAR-2 of 22h faster than MapleCOMSPS strategy; H_{ratio} -based strategy solves 2 UNSAT and 13 SAT instances more with a PAR-2 of 33h faster than MapleCOMSPS strategy. A detailed observation shows that the presented heuristics win all but the guarantee and the obligation

¹⁰ PAR-k is the penalised average runtime, counting each timeout as k times the running time cutoff.

Fig. 7. Scatter-plot of the two heuristics H_{size} versus H_{ratio}

LTL category, especially, a clear improvement can be appreciated (up to 6 more instances solved) for the safety and reactivity classes.

It appears that H_{ratio} performs slightly better than H_{size} heuristic (6 more instances in total with PAR-2 of 11h faster). This is a direct consequence of the way we build H_{ratio} . Indeed, in this strategy, we enforce more constraints of the linear program to fit the relative importance of each class C_X . Figure 7 presents the scatter-plot comparison of H_{size} and H_{ratio} heuristics pointing out two information (highlighted by the green rectangles): in one hand H_{size} manages to solve more UNSAT instances than H_{ratio} (red points are above the diagonal line). In the other hand H_{ratio} is better on solving SAT instances (blue dots are focus under the diagonal line). This suggest that a portfolio approach combining these two heuristics could bring ever more performances.

Discussion. From the previous experiments, we conclude that (1) tuning the selector for a same volume of involved clauses H_{size} than traditional selector, improves the results but (2) a sophisticated strategy H_{ratio} offer better and significant improvements, especially for detecting satisfiable formulas. Consequently, we recommend to build dedicated (problem-specific) selectors for managing the database of clauses. However, it should be noted that building such an efficient strategy requires a deep understanding on the structure of the underlying problem.

8 Related work

Most of the existing work focus on building generic approaches for tuning SAT solver. They rarely exploit the information deriving from the original problem.

In this paper, we focus our studies on the BMC problem offering two main characteristics: the classification of clauses and the specificity of the studied LTL property. To our knowledge, the combination of these two elements have never been studied in this context. The closest work is the one of [26] that can be considered at the foundation stone of this work. In this prior study, we suggested a generic approach to partition clauses and exploit this information during the SAT solving. Other work [38, 44, 21, 43] present a variety of optimizations such as: variable ordering heuristics, branching heuristics, studying the symmetry structure of the BMC Boolean formula. These works could be refined using the two information exploited in this paper. The decomposition of the BMC formula into simpler and independent subproblems has also been investigated [18, 19]. Nonetheless they do not focus on the categorization of the variables handled by the clauses and thus remains more generic than our approach.

Finally, the hierarchy of Manna and Pnueli [29] has been used to tune explicit model-checker [35, 15, 17]. These studies propose to decompose the input automaton, or propose optimizations for specific classes of the hierarchy. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first covering all the classes of this hierarchy in the context of SAT-based BMC. Others works focus mainly on safety properties [3, 37, 23, 22].

9 Conclusion

In this paper we proposed to exploit the information extracted from the BMC problem in order to improve their solving by existing SAT solvers. Our approach focuses on tuning one of the main components of CDCL-like SAT solvers: the database of learnt clauses. Such databases usually use generic metrics (such as LBD) to identify and preserve relevant learnt clauses.

In this paper, we propose a refinement of these metrics with structural information extracted from the model and/or the property at hand. In addition, we propose to exploit deeper the hierarchy of Manna & Pnueli to tune the optimization procedures according to the studied LTL property. Combining all the aforementioned (static and dynamic) information lead us to define selectors that identify relevant learnt clauses.

We then proposed two heuristics: a constraint-free approach H_{size} , and a guided approach that integrates more information of the studied problem H_{ratio} .

These two last, experimented over a large set of BMC problems, surpass the state-of-the-art approach on both SAT and UNSAT instances. These experiments also highlight the effectiveness of building dedicated heuristics according to the information carried by the original problem.

Future work aims to apply the presented heuristics in the context of parallel SAT solvers, especially to propose new sharing strategies to detect relevant clauses that must be shared within a portfolio parallel strategy. We also would like to propagate this study to investigate deeper other part of the SAT resolution such as: purging the databases, branching strategies and variable ordering approaches.

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